

On the Metal Ion-Coordinating Properties of the Antiviral Nucleotide Analogue 9-[2-(Phosphonomethoxy)ethyl]adenine and Related Compounds[#]

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To be chosen by the *Indian Chemical Society* as the recipient of the *Professor Priyadarajan Ray Award* for the year 1996 is an outstanding honour. To be further allowed to deliver the connected *Memorial Lecture* is a proud privilege, indeed. Priyadarajan Ray, great as a scientist, greater as a man¹, has set high marks worth to emulate.

Recently, in working with a derivative of adenosine 5'-monophosphate, i.e. a compound in which one of the oxygens of the phosphate residue is replaced by a sulphur atom and which is named adenosine 5'-*O*-thiomonophosphate (Fig. 1), I came across the work of Professor Priyadarajan Ray. The mentioned derivative is evidently an ambivalent ligand and the question arises, where does

Fig. 1. Chemical structure of adenosine 5'-*O*-thiomonophosphate (AMPS²⁻) in its *anti*-conformation.

the proton bind at the thiophosphate group? Is it at the sulphur atom or at one of the oxygens? Of course, the same question also arises for metal ions. In dealing with these questions I studied a publication by Japanese colleagues from the year 1959 devoted to monothiophosphate² and in this work it is concluded that *trans*-bisethylenediamine-cobalt(III) binds two monothiophosphate ions via the sulphur atoms and in this identification procedure the studies on thiosulphatocobalt(III) complexes carried out by P. Ray³ in 1927 and by P. Ray and S. Maulik⁴ in 1933 have played a significant role. I believe this incident demonstrates nicely how we all are standing on the shoulders of those who worked before us – and therefore, hopefully we can see a little bit further and for this we should be grateful! Or, to say it in the words of Priyadarajan Ray himself: ... "knowledge and wisdom grow only on the accumulated in-

terests of the past"...⁵. I shall now not dwell further on the achievements of Professor P. Ray, these have been summarised in the most competent way by Professor Banerjee and published in the *Journal of the Indian Chemical Society*¹, and also not on the acid-base⁶ and metal ion-binding properties⁷ of adenosine 5'-*O*-thiomonophosphate, which were described elsewhere^{6,7}, but instead I would like to focus now on the metal ion-coordinating properties of antiviral nucleotide analogues.

On the metabolic role of nucleotides and their antimetabolites

Nucleotides play a central role in all kinds of metabolic processes⁸⁻¹⁰. To give just a single example: Each person synthesises per day approximately the amount of adenosine 5'-triphosphate (ATP⁴⁻) corresponding to the own body weight and of course, uses it again¹¹. Considering this tremendous role played by nucleotides it is not surprising that there have been many attempts to synthesise nucleotide analogues with the aim to obtain therapeutically usable agents¹²⁻¹⁴. One of the difficulties is that base- or sugar-modified analogues with monophosphate-ester residues undergo enzyme-catalysed dephosphorylation during their passage through the cellular membrane or in blood plasma¹⁵ rendering therapeutic application of such anti-metabolites inefficient. This difficulty is circumvented by applying analogues with a phosphonate residue¹⁵, i.e. the phosphorus-oxygen ester bond is replaced by a phosphorus-carbon bond.

One of these nucleotide analogues with a phosphonate residue is 9-[2-(phosphonomethoxy)ethyl]adenine (PMEA; Fig. 2). It shows antiviral properties¹⁶ and may be considered as an analogue of adenosine 5'-monophosphate (5'-AMP²⁻). PMEA is active against DNA viruses, like herpes, adeno, or pox viruses^{16,17}, and also against retroviruses, like human immunodeficiency (HIV) and Moloney murine sarcoma (MSV) viruses¹⁶⁻¹⁹. PMEA and related phosphonate derivatives are converted by cellular nucleotide kinases into their diphosphates, i.e. PMEA²⁻ is transformed into an ATP⁴⁻ or 2'-deoxy-ATP⁴⁻ analogue²⁰, and as such they inhibit viral and, to a lesser extent, cellular DNA synthesis^{17,20,21}. Specifically, the diphosphorylated PMEA analogue acts as an inhibitor of DNA polymerase and exerts its antiviral activity as a DNA chain terminator²¹.

At this point it is important to note that nucleotides

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participate as co-enzymes in enzymic reactions only in the form of metal ion complexes^{10,22-24}. Furthermore, DNA and RNA polymerases are mostly Zn²⁺ metalloenzymes^{9,25}, which generally use the Mg²⁺ complexes of their nucleotide substrates. With the indicated roles of metal ions in mind it is appealing to study the metal ion-binding properties of PME²⁻_A²⁶⁻²⁹ and related phosphonates³⁰⁻³².

Preliminary comparison of some properties of 5'-AMP and PME²⁻

Let us first compare the metal ion-binding properties of 5'-AMP and PME²⁻, the structures of which are shown^{33,34} in Fig. 2. We include into this comparison also the dianion of (phosphonomethoxy)ethane (PME²⁻)²⁶ because this should allow us to quantify the effect of the adenine residue on the metal ion-binding properties of PME²⁻. It is important to recall at this point that in various M(AMP) complexes macrochelates are formed^{35,36}, giving rise to the intramolecular equilibrium (1),

where a metal ion not only binds to the phosphate group but also to N7 of the purine residue^{22,23,35,36}. Consequently, the question arises about a similar nucleobase backbinding in M(PME²⁻) complexes.

Any metal-ion interaction in addition to that at the phosph(on)ate group has to be reflected in an increased stability³⁷; this means, in a complex stability which is higher than that expected on the basis of the basicity of the corresponding phosph(on)ate group. Therefore, over the years we have determined the acid-base and metal ion-binding properties of simple phosphate monoesters^{38,39}, like phenyl phosphate, and phosphonates²⁶, like methylphosphonate. For such compounds R-PO₃²⁻, where R represents a non-coordinating residue, the positions of the following equilibria were determined :

The corresponding equilibrium data allow the construction of log K_{M(R-PO₃)}}^M versus pK_{H(R-PO₃)}}^H plots which result in straight-lines. The corresponding straight-line reference-equations can easily be calculated²⁶ and be used to evaluate increased complex stabilities. Such an example is shown in Fig. 3 for the Ca²⁺ and Cd²⁺ complexes of the ligands seen in Fig. 2.

Without any calculations, the following facts are evident at once from Fig. 3. (i) For Cd(5'-AMP) the in-

Fig 2 Chemical structure of the dianion of 9-[2-(phosphonomethoxy)ethyl]adenine (PME²⁻) in comparison with the structures of adenosine 5'-monophosphate (5'-AMP²⁻) and the dianion of (phosphonomethoxy)ethane (PME²⁻ = ethoxymethanephosphonate), 5'-AMP²⁻ is shown in its dominating *anti*-conformation^{33,34}

tramolecular equilibrium (1) is operating, as the increased stability of this complex confirms. (ii) From the stability of the Cd²⁺ complex of tubercidin 5'-monophosphate (TuMP²⁻ = 7-deaza-5'-AMP²⁻) it follows immediately that macrochelate formation must occur with N7 because the only difference between 5'-AMP²⁻ and TuMP²⁻ is that in the latter N7 has been replaced by a CH unit. (iii) The stability data for Ca(5'-AMP) and Ca(TuMP) fall within their error limits on the reference line indicating that the stability of these two complexes is solely determined by the basicity of the corresponding -PO₃²⁻ group, i.e. these two complexes occur only, or at least *overwhelmingly*, in the 'open' form of equilibrium (1). (iv) The Ca²⁺ and Cd²⁺ complexes of PME²⁻ own an increased complex stability! This must mean that the following intramolecular equilibrium (4) is operating,

because there is no further binding site but the ether oxygen available in PME^{2-} (*cf.* Fig. 2). (v). The stabilities of the $\text{Ca}(\text{PMEA})$ and $\text{Cd}(\text{PMEA})$ complexes are also clearly above the reference lines. As the stability increase is comparable to the one observed with the corresponding $\text{M}(\text{PME})$ complexes, this indicates that for the mentioned $\text{M}(\text{PMEA})$ complexes also equilibrium (4) is operating. Moreover, especially the comparison of the stabilities of the $\text{Ca}(5'\text{-AMP})$ and $\text{Ca}(\text{PMEA})$ complexes indicates that the $\text{M}(5'\text{-AMP})$ and $\text{M}(\text{PMEA})$ species own different structures in solution !

Quantification of intramolecular equilibria involving two isomers : Complexes of $5'\text{-AMP}^{2-}$, PME^{2-} and PMEA^{2-}

The above conclusions can be quantified by calculating the following stability differences, where PA^{2-} [P for phosph(on)ate, and A, for adenine; see also the two subsequent Sections] represents $5'\text{-AMP}^{2-}$, PMEA^{2-} , PME^{2-} or any other nucleotide or its analogues :

$$\log \Delta_{\text{M/PA}} = \log K_{\text{M}(\text{PA})}^{\text{M}} - \log K_{\text{M}(\text{PA})_{\text{op}}}^{\text{M}} \quad (5a)$$

$$= \log K_{\text{M}(\text{PA})_{\text{exp}}}^{\text{M}} - K_{\text{M}(\text{PA})_{\text{calc}}}^{\text{M}} \quad (5b)$$

Values for $\log K_{\text{M}(\text{PA})}^{\text{M}}$ are experimentally accessible (in analogy to equation 3) and therefore sometimes termed as $\log K_{\text{M}(\text{PA})_{\text{exp}}}^{\text{M}}$ and those for $\log K_{\text{M}(\text{PA})_{\text{op}}}^{\text{M}}$ can be calculated (hence also termed as $\log K_{\text{M}(\text{PA})_{\text{calc}}}^{\text{M}}$) by employing the previously published straight-line equations^{26,36} and the values for $\text{p}K_{\text{H}(\text{PA})}^{\text{H}}$ quantifying the deprotonation of the mono-protonated phosph(on)ate group of the $\text{H}(\text{PA})^-$ species. In this way the stability of the $\text{M}(\text{PA})_{\text{op}}$ complex, i.e. of the open form in the intramolecular equilibria (1) and (4), is obtained. It may be added that the straight-line equations are based on the simple R-PO_3^{2-} ligands listed in the legend of Fig. 3. The stability difference $\log \Delta_{\text{M/PA}}$ corresponds to the vertical distances seen in Fig. 3 between the solid data points and their corresponding reference lines. This stability difference is also connected with the dimensionless equilibrium constant K_1 (equation 6)

$$K_1 = [\text{M}(\text{PA})_{\text{cl}}]/[\text{M}(\text{PA})_{\text{op}}] \quad (6)$$

which quantifies the position of the intramolecular equilibria (1) and (4), and where the closed form is represented by $\text{M}(\text{PA})_{\text{cl}}$, via the definitions given in equations (7) and (8),

$$K_{\text{M}(\text{PA})}^{\text{M}} = \frac{([\text{M}(\text{PA})_{\text{op}}] + [\text{M}(\text{PA})_{\text{cl}}])}{[\text{M}^{2+}][\text{PA}^{2-}]} \quad (7b)$$

$$= \frac{[\text{M}(\text{PA})_{\text{op}}]}{[\text{M}^{2+}][\text{PA}^{2-}]} + \frac{[\text{M}(\text{PA})_{\text{cl}}]}{[\text{M}^{2+}][\text{PA}^{2-}]} \quad (7c)$$

$$= K_{\text{M}(\text{PA})_{\text{op}}}^{\text{M}} + K_1 K_{\text{M}(\text{PA})_{\text{op}}}^{\text{M}} \quad (7d)$$

$$= K_{\text{M}(\text{PA})_{\text{op}}}^{\text{M}} (1 + K_1) \quad (7e)$$

$$K_1 = \frac{K_{\text{M}(\text{PA})}^{\text{M}}}{K_{\text{M}(\text{PA})_{\text{op}}}^{\text{M}}} - 1 = 10^{\log \Delta} - 1 \quad (8)$$

where, $\log \Delta = \log \Delta_{\text{M/PA}}$ (equation 5).

Fig. 3. Evidence for an enhanced stability of several $\text{M}(\text{PME})$, $\text{M}(\text{PMEA})$, and $\text{M}(5'\text{-AMP})$ [= $\text{M}(\text{PA})$] complexes (●), based on the relationship between $\log K_{\text{M}(\text{R-PO}_3)}^{\text{M}}$ and $\text{p}K_{\text{H}(\text{R-PO}_3)}^{\text{H}}$ for the 1 : 1 complexes of Ca^{2+} and Cd^{2+} with some simple phosphate monoester or phosphonate ligands (R-PO_3^{2-}) : 4-nitrophenyl phosphate (NPhP^{2-}), phenyl phosphate (PhP^{2-}), uridine 5'-monophosphate (UMP^{2-}), D-ribose 5-monophosphate (RibMP^{2-}), thymidine [=1-(2-deoxy-β-D-ribofuranosyl)thymine] 5'-monophosphate (dTMP^{2-}), n-butyl phosphate (BuP^{2-}), methanephosphonate (MeP^{2-}), and ethanephosphonate (EtP^{2-}) (from left to right) (○). The least-squares lines are drawn through the corresponding eight data sets taken from Ref. 38 for the phosphate monoesters and from Ref. 26 for the phosphonates; the equations for these base lines are given in Refs. 26 and 36. The data for the points due to the AMP or PME and PME systems (●) are taken from Refs. 35 and 26, respectively. The vertical broken lines emphasise the stability differences to the corresponding reference lines; these differences equal $\log \Delta_{\text{M/PA}}$ as defined by eqn. (5). The points for the complexes with TuMP^{2-} (=7-deaza-AMP²⁻; ⊕) fall within the error limits on the reference lines; the log stability constants of the $\text{M}(\text{TuMP})$ complexes are plotted versus the microconstant $\text{p}K_{\text{TuMPH}}^{\text{H}} = 6.24$ and these data are taken from Table 3 and Fig. 2 of Ref. 35, respectively. All the plotted equilibrium constant values refer to aqueous solutions at 25° and $I = 0.1 \text{ M}$ (NaNO_3).

In Table 1 the results regarding equilibria (1) and (4) are summarised for the complexes $\text{M}(5'\text{-AMP})$ and $\text{M}(\text{PMEA})$ or $\text{M}(\text{PME})$, respectively. These results confirm the conclusions already given in the previous Section on the basis of Fig. 3. This means, the formation degree of macrochelates for the alkaline earth ions is zero within the

TABLE 1—COMPARISON OF THE STABILITY INCREASES, $\log \Delta_{M/PA}$ (EQNS. 5,8), DUE TO CHELATE FORMATION AS SEEN IN EQUILIBRIA (1) AND (4), AND OF THE FORMATION DEGREE OF THESE CHELATES, % $M(PA)_{cl}$ (EQNS. 6,7), IN VARIOUS $M(PA)$ COMPLEXES IN AQUEOUS SOLUTION AT 25° AND $I = 0.1 M$ ($NaNO_3$)^{a,b}

M^{2+}	$M(5'-AMP)^c$		$M(PMEA)^c$		$M(PME)^c$	
	$\log \Delta_{M/AMP}$	% $M(AMP)_{cl}$	$\log \Delta_{M/PMEA}$	% $M(PMEA)_{cl}$	$\log \Delta_{M/PME}$	% $M(PME)_{cl}$
Mg^{2+}	0.04 ± 0.04	0 (<17)	0.16 ± 0.05	31 ± 8	0.22 ± 0.03	40 ± 4
Ca^{2+}	0.01 ± 0.05	0 (<13)	0.11 ± 0.07	22 ± 13	0.14 ± 0.05	28 ± 9
Sr^{2+}	0.00 ± 0.04	0 (<9)	0.07 ± 0.05	15 ± 10	0.07 ± 0.05	15 ± 10
Ba^{2+}	0.01 ± 0.04	0 (<11)	0.08 ± 0.06	17 ± 12	0.10 ± 0.05	21 ± 9
Mn^{2+}	0.07 ± 0.05	15 ± 10	0.21 ± 0.08	38 ± 11	0.27 ± 0.05	46 ± 7
Co^{2+}	0.29 ± 0.06	49 ± 7	0.28 ± 0.07	48 ± 8	0.29 ± 0.06	49 ± 7
Ni^{2+}	0.55 ± 0.05	72 ± 3	0.30 ± 0.07	(50 ± 8) ^e	0.19 ± 0.05	35 ± 8
Cu^{2+}	0.27 ± 0.06	46 ± 8	0.77 ± 0.07	(83 ± 3) ^e	0.48 ± 0.07	67 ± 5
Zn^{2+}	0.25 ± 0.09	44 ± 12	0.30 ± 0.10 ^d	50 ± 12	0.34 ± 0.06	54 ± 7
Cd^{2+}	0.24 ± 0.05	42 ± 7	0.33 ± 0.06	53 ± 7	0.30 ± 0.05	50 ± 6

^aThe error limits are three times the standard error of the mean value or the sum of the probable systematic errors, whichever is larger; the error limits of the derived values were calculated according to the error propagation after Gauss.

^bWith eqn. (8) and the above given $\log \Delta_{M/PA}$ values the constants K_1 are calculated; from these follows % $M(PA)_{cl} = 100 K_1 / (K_1 + 1)$.

^cThe values for $M(5'-AMP)$ are from Ref. 36 (cf. also Ref. 22), those for $M(PMEA)$ and $M(PME)$ are from Ref. 26.

^dThis value is only an estimate due to precipitation; see Ref. 26.

^eSee text in Section 'Evidence for .. $M(PMEA)$ complexes'.

error limits for their complexes with $5'-AMP^{2-}$, whereas the $3d$ ions, including Zn^{2+} and Cd^{2+} form appreciable amounts of macrochelates involving N7. Similarly, the formation degree of the five-membered chelate according to equilibrium (4) is of significance for all the $M(PME)$ and $M(PMEA)$ complexes studied. Furthermore, a careful comparison of the values listed for $\log \Delta_{M/PMEA}$ with those for $\log \Delta_{M/PME}$ (Table 1, columns 4 and 6) reveals that they are identical within their error-limits except for the complexes of Ni^{2+} and Cu^{2+} . For these two metal ions the $PMEA^{2-}$ complexes are more stable than those formed with PME^{2-} .

Evidence for a metal ion-adenine interaction in certain $M(PMEA)$ complexes

The mentioned additional stability increase may be quantified according to equation (9),

$$\Delta \log \Delta_{M/PA} = \log \Delta_{M/PA} - \log \Delta_{M/PME} \quad (9)$$

where PA^{2-} represents $PMEA^{2-}$ or any of its derivatives, and it amounts for $Cu(PMEA)$ to $\Delta \log \Delta_{Cu/PMEA} = (0.77 \pm 0.07) - (0.48 \pm 0.07) = 0.29 \pm 0.10$ (Table 1). This means, in the $PMEA^{2-}$ complexes of Cu^{2+} and Ni^{2+} ($\Delta \log \Delta_{Ni/PMEA} = 0.11 \pm 0.09$) there must be in addition to the formation of the five-membered chelate involving the ether oxygen (equilibrium 4) a further interaction involving the adenine residue. For this reason the values given in Table 1 for $Ni(PMEA)_{cl}$ and $Cu(PMEA)_{cl}$ are in parentheses.

Especially the above mentioned result for the $Cu(PMEA)$ complex is unequivocal. Hence, the question arises : which of the potential binding sites of the adenine residue, i.e. N1, N3, or N7 is participating in the additional interaction of the (at least) already phosphonate-coor-

dated metal ion ? Space filling molecular models show²⁶ that a metal ion bound to the phosphonate group cannot reach N1; this leaves N3 and N7 for a further coordination. These two cases are considered in the following two equilibrium schemes, where PA^{2-} represents again $PMEA^{2-}$ or any of its derivatives. In the first case (equilibrium 10),

the pure phosphonate-coordinated species is designated as $M(PA)_{op}$, the five-membered chelate involving the ether O atom (equation 4) as $M(PA)_{cl/O}$ and the macrochelated species involving N7 as $M(PA)_{cl/N7}$. A simultaneous binding of a phosphonate-bound metal ion to the ether O atom and to N7 is for steric reasons not possible. The second scheme consists of the successive equilibria (11),

Here $M(PA)_{cl/O/N3}$ represents the two-fold chelated species involving the ether O atom and N3; it needs to be mentioned that molecular models indicate²⁶ that the formation of a macrochelate involving only the phosphonate group and N3 is highly unlikely because the formation of such a species would force the ether O atom into the coordination sphere of the metal ion²⁶. In other words, a metal ion che-

lated to the phosphonate and the ether O atom (equation 4) may also interact with N3 by forming a seven-membered chelate without disrupting the ether O-M²⁺ bond. The other definitions used in the equilibrium scheme (11) are the same as given above with the equilibrium scheme (10).

Which of the adenine-bound isomers, M(PMEA)_{c1/N7} or M(PMEA)_{c1/O/N3}, is now actually formed? Or, are even both isomers present at the same time? To resolve these questions we included in our studies the N1, N3, and N7 deaza derivatives of PMEAs, which are shown in Fig. 4.

Acid-base properties of PMEAs and its deaza derivatives

To be able to evaluate the metal ion-binding properties of the deaza derivatives (Fig. 4) it was necessary to study first their acid-base properties and especially to identify, in each case, the site at which the proton is bound at the adenine residue in the H₂(PA)[±] species, where PA²⁻ = PMEAs²⁻, 1-deaza-PMEAs²⁻, 3-deaza-PMEAs²⁻ or 7-deaza-PMEAs²⁻. To achieve this goal we have measured⁴⁰ the chemical shifts of the protons of all the mentioned PMEAs in D₂O in dependence on pD in the approximate pD range 0–12.

In Fig. 5 the chemical shifts in dependence on pD are shown for two examples, i.e. for all the hydrogens of PMEAs as well as of its 3-deaza derivative. The variation of

the chemical shifts of the hydrogens in dependence on pD follows to a large part the general expectation, i.e. that protonation leads to a decrease of electron density and thus, to a shift of the signals to lower field (i.e. to larger ppm values). However, in various instances also so-called wrongway shifts^{34,41} are observed, but these have been discussed in detail recently elsewhere⁴⁰ and therefore are not discussed further. For the present it is important to note that for PMEAs, and 3-deaza-PMEAs as well, clearly four 'turning points' are observed; namely, for PMEAs at pD about 7.5, 4.5, 2, and 0.5, the latter two become visible only if the shifts of H8 and P-CH₂ are compared. The pK_a value responsible for the shift of the P-CH₂ signal in the pD range from 0–3 is clearly higher than the one responsible for the downfield shift of the signals of H8 and H2 in the same pD region. Indeed, such comparisons allow the attribution of the various pK_a values to certain sites⁴⁰. In addition, it is clear from Fig. 5 that PMEAs²⁻ can accept four protons in total, i.e. under very strong acidic conditions in aqueous solution the species H₄(PMEAs)²⁺ forms. The first proton added to PMEAs²⁻ binds at the -PO₂⁻ group, the second at N1 of the adenine residue, the third at the -PO₂(OH)⁻ group and the final, fourth at N7. The same is true for 1-deaza-PMEAs²⁻ and 3-deaza-PMEAs²⁻, whereas 7-deaza-PMEAs²⁻, due to the absence of N7, accepts in the

Fig. 4. Chemical structures of the deaza derivatives of PMEAs²⁻: 1-deaza-PMEAs²⁻, 3-deaza-PMEAs²⁻, and 7-deaza-PMEAs²⁻. For example, 1-deaza-PMEAs, named 9-[2-(phosphonomethoxy)ethyl]-1-deazaadenine, is sometimes also abbreviated as 1d-PMEAs²⁻.

Fig. 5. Variation of the chemical shifts for all aromatic and aliphatic protons in dependence on pD for 5 mM PMEAs and 7 mM 3-deaza-PMEAs in D₂O at 25° (at pD ≥ 1, I = 0.1 M NaNO₃; at pD < 1, I increased to 0.3 M). The curves are the computer-calculated best fits of the experimental data using the average of the individually determined pK_a values. For details see Ref. 40.

mentioned pD range in total only three protons. As the first two protons of $H_4(PA)^{2+}$ are released with $pK_{a/4} \sim 0$ (from $H^+(N7)$) and $pK_{a/3} \sim 1.2$ (from $-PO(OH)_2$), the corresponding deprotonation reactions are not of further interest in the present context which focuses more on the physiological pH range. The deprotonation of the $H_2(PA)^{\pm}$ species occurs in a pH region which is also accessible by potentiometric pH-titrations of aqueous (H_2O) solutions. The corresponding results for all the mentioned PMEAs are summarised in Table 2 together with some related data^{34,35,38,42}. The deprotonation sites are also given in this Table.

Table 2 allows many comparisons; a few will be given, others are left to the interested reader. For example, (i) the value of $K_{H(Ado)}^H$ confirms that the $K_{H_2(PA)}^H$ values for $H_2(5'-AMP)^{\pm}$ and $H_2(PMEA)^{\pm}$ are due to the deprotonation of the adenine residue. (ii) The deaza compounds always own an increased basicity in their deazaadenine residue compared with the properties of the parent adenine residue; this is understandable, as an electronegative nitrogen is replaced by a CH unit. (iii) Similarly, replacement of the P-O ester bond by a P-C bond makes the phosphonate residue somewhat more basic than the phosphate residue.

Finally, it may be added that for several of the $H_2(PA)^{\pm}$ species listed in Table 2, the buffer regions for the release of the two protons are overlapping. This made it necessary to develop microconstant schemes and to evaluate in this way the actual acid-base properties of certain sites^{35,40}. In the present context it is only important to note that the two pK_a values of $H_2(PMEA)^{\pm}$ are separated by $\Delta pK_a = 2.74$ (cf. Table 2); hence, the corresponding buffer regions are

TABLE 2—NEGATIVE LOGARITHMS OF THE ACIDITY CONSTANTS FOR $H(Ado)^+$, $H(Tu)^+$, $H(RibMP)$, AND OF VARIOUS $H_2(PA)^{\pm}$ SPECIES (IN ANALOGY TO EQN 2)

as determined by potentiometric pH-titrations in aqueous solution at 25° and $I = 0.1 M (NaNO_3)$, together with the site being deprotonated (cf. Figs 2 and 4)^a

Protonated species	$pK_{H_2(PA)}^H$ $H^+(N1)$	$pK_{H(PA)}^H$ $-PO_2(OH)^-$	Ref
$H(Ado)^+$	3.61 ± 0.03^b		34
$H(RibMP)$		6.24 ± 0.01	38
$H_2(5'-AMP)^{\pm}$	3.84 ± 0.02	6.21 ± 0.01	35
$H(Tu)^+$	5.21 ± 0.03^c		42
$H_2(TuMP)^{\pm}$	5.28 ± 0.02	6.32 ± 0.01	35
$H(PME)^-$		7.02 ± 0.01	26
$H_2(PMEA)^{\pm}$	4.16 ± 0.02	6.90 ± 0.01	26
$H_2(1\text{-deaza-PMEA})^{\pm}$	5.49 ± 0.02^d	7.03 ± 0.02	40
$H_2(3\text{-deaza-PMEA})^{\pm}$	6.61 ± 0.02	7.83 ± 0.01	40
$H_2(7\text{-deaza-PMEA})^{\pm}$	5.62 ± 0.02	7.00 ± 0.01	40

^acf footnote (a) of Table 1 Abbreviations Ado, adenosine, RibMP²⁻, D-ribose 5-monophosphate. Tu, tubercidin (=7-deaza-Ado), TuMP²⁻, tubercidin 5'-monophosphate (=7-deaza-5'-AMP²⁻), see also Figs 2 and 4

^bThis value refers to $pK_{H(Ado)}^H$.

^cThis value refers to $pK_{H(Tu)}^H$.

^dDeprotonation of the nucleobase moiety in $H_2(1\text{-deaza-PMEA})^{\pm}$ occurs at the $H^+(N3)$ site, see Ref 40

hardly overlapping in this case and $pK_{H(PMEA)}^H = 6.90$ represents well the acidic properties of the $-PO_2(OH)^-$ group. For the deaza derivatives of PMEAs it was concluded⁴⁰ that the micro-acidity constant, which represents best the properties of their $-PO_2(OH)^-$ group, is also given by the mentioned value, i.e. $pK_{H(PA)}^H = pK_{H(PMEA)}^H = 6.90$. In those cases where the buffer regions overlap the $H(PA)^-$ species exists in two isomeric forms, namely, $(H^+PA)^-$ and $(PA^+H)^-$, where the proton is bound to the phosphonate group or the adenine residue, respectively. The mentioned micro-acidity constant will be needed below in some of the evaluations (e.g., Fig. 6 and Table 3, *vide infra*).

Stabilities of the Cu^{2+} complexes of $PMEA^{2-}$ and its deaza derivatives

With the acid-base properties of PMEAs and its deaza derivatives at hand, the stability constants for the various

Fig 6 Evidence for an enhanced stability of the Cu^{2+} 1:1 complexes $[=Cu(PA)]$ with PME^{2-} , $PMEA^{2-}$, 1-deaza- $PMEA^{2-}$, 3-deaza- $PMEA^{2-}$, and 7-deaza- $PMEA^{2-}$ (●), based on the relationship between $\log K_{Cu(R-PO_3)}$ and $pK_{H(R-PO_3)}$ for the 1:1 complexes of Cu^{2+} with some simple phosphate monoester or phosphonate ligands ($R-PO_3^{\pm}$), the abbreviations used above for these ligands (O) are defined in the legend of Fig 3 For information regarding the straight reference-line see also there The data points for the complexes of $5'-AMP^{2-}$ and $TuMP^{2-}$ (=7-deaza- $5'-AMP^{2-}$) (●) are given for comparison The points due to the equilibrium constants for the Cu^{2+}/PA^{2-} systems (●) are based on the acidity constants and stability constants listed in Tables 2 and 3, respectively, but for 1-deaza- $PMEA^{2-}$, 3-deaza- $PMEA^{2-}$ and 7-deaza- $PMEA^{2-}$ the micro-acidity constant, $pK_{H(PA)}^H = 6.90$, and for $TuMP^{2-}$, $pK_{TuMP}^H = 6.24$ (see Fig 2 in Ref 35) are used The vertical broken lines emphasise the stability differences to the reference line, these differences equal $\log \Delta C_{Cu/PA}$ as defined by eqn (5) All the plotted equilibrium constant values refer to aqueous solutions at 25° and $I = 0.1 M (NaNO_3)$

Cu(PA) complexes were measured by potentiometric pH-titrations⁴³. We restricted ourselves in this case to the Cu²⁺ complexes because Cu²⁺ shows a pronounced affinity toward N donor sites⁴⁴ and this should facilitate the possibility to quantify adenine-Cu²⁺ interactions as summarised in the equilibrium schemes (10) and (11).

In Fig. 6 the results are plotted in the way as described before for Fig. 3. It is evident that the data points (full circles) for the Cu²⁺ complexes of PMEA and its derivatives rest significantly above the reference line and that their stability increases are larger than that of Cu(PME). Thus, in the Cu²⁺ complexes of PMEA²⁻ and of all of its derivatives shown in Fig. 4, a nucleobase-Cu²⁺ interaction must occur. Moreover, a comparison of the data point for Cu(5'-AMP) with those due to the Cu²⁺ complexes of the PMEAs shows that chelate formation must be considerably more important in the latter cases. It may also be emphasised that the data point for the Cu(TuMP) complex fits on the reference line, confirming the already mentioned conclusion that macrochelate formation in Cu(5'-AMP) occurs with N7.

A quantitative evaluation of the data given in Fig. 6 is possible and application of equations (5) and (9) leads to the results summarised in Table 3. The entries in the first two rows confirm the above conclusions regarding Cu(5'-AMP). Furthermore, the values listed in column 5 of the table for $\Delta \log \Delta_{\text{Cu/PA}}$ (equation 9) are all positive, proving that the equilibrium schemes (10) and (11) are operating indeed, in the case of Cu(PMEA) as well as for the complexes of the deaza derivatives.

Identification of the metal ion-binding sites at the nucleobase residue in the Cu(PMEA) species

Which nitrogen atoms of the various adenine residues are involved in Cu²⁺ binding? For Cu(3-deaza-PMEA) it is

clear that aside from the interactions defined in equilibrium (4) only a further interaction with N7 is possible; consequently, in this case equilibrium scheme (10) must be operating and thus, the structure of the macrochelate will resemble that found for Cu(5'-AMP) (*cf.* equilibrium 1). The next clearcut case is the Cu²⁺ complex of 7-deaza-PMEA²⁻ (Fig. 4), though in this case the stability increase observed beyond the one for Cu(PME) is relatively small (*cf.* Table 3, column 5). However, this small stability increase can only be due to a Cu²⁺-N3 interaction, which means that equilibrium scheme (11) is operating.

How is the situation for Cu(PMEA) and Cu(1-deaza-PMEA)? Careful considerations, including the use of molecular models, led to the suggestion²⁶ that the equilibrium scheme (11) involving the Cu(PMEA)_{G1/O/N3} isomer is the pertinent one. This suggestion is further supported by the very large stability increase observed⁴³ for the Cu(1-deaza-PMEA) complex because in 1-deaza-PMEA²⁻ N3 is by far the most basic site⁴⁰ of this deazaadenine residue. However, to provide a more unequivocal answer to the above question we carried out ¹H nmr line-broadening studies⁴³ by making use of the paramagnetic properties of Cu²⁺. The most pertinent of these results are summarised in Fig. 7. From the top of this figure it is evident that for PMEA²⁻, if titrated with Cu²⁺, the signal of H2 is considerably more broadened than the one due to H8. This dominant effect on H2 may indicate chelate formation with N3 rather than N7. However, a monodentate binding of Cu²⁺ at N1 could produce a similar line broadening of the H2 signal. Clearly, this latter interpretation is ruled out by the observations made with 1-deaza-PMEA²⁻ (see the middle part of Fig. 7). The signal of H2 of 1-deaza-PMEA²⁻ is very strongly broadened by Cu²⁺ despite the fact that no N1 site is present anymore in this deaza derivative. Hence, the phosphonate group exer-

TABLE 3—STABILITY CONSTANT COMPARISONS BETWEEN MEASURED STABILITY CONSTANTS (EXP.) AND CALCULATED STABILITY CONSTANTS (CALC.)^a FOR THE Cu(PA) COMPLEXES OF 5'-AMP²⁻, TuMP²⁻, PME²⁻, PMEA²⁻ AND THE DEAZA DERIVATIVES OF PMEA²⁻. IN ADDITION, VALUES FOR $\Delta \log \Delta_{\text{Cu/PA}}$ (EQN. 9) ARE GIVEN WHICH REFLECT THE FURTHER STABILITY INCREASE DUE TO A NUCLEOBASE-Cu²⁺ INTERACTION IN THE COMPLEXES OF PMEA²⁻ AND ITS DEAZA DERIVATIVES

Aqueous solutions; *I* = 0.1 M, NaNO₃; 25^{ob}

PA ²⁻	$\log K_{\text{Cu(PA)}}^c$		$\log \Delta_{\text{Cu/PA}}$ (Eqn. 5)	$\Delta \log \Delta_{\text{Cu/PA}}$ (Eqn. 9)	Ref
	Exp.	Calc. ^a			
5'-AMP ²⁻	3.14 ± 0.01	2.87 ± 0.06	0.27 ± 0.06		36
TuMP ²⁻	2.90 ± 0.08	2.89 ± 0.06 ^d	0.01 ± 0.06		35 ^d
PME ²⁻	3.73 ± 0.03	3.25 ± 0.06	0.48 ± 0.07		26
PMEA ²⁻	3.96 ± 0.04	3.19 ± 0.06	0.77 ± 0.07	0.29 ± 0.10	26
1-deaza-PMEA ²⁻	4.66 ± 0.08	3.19 ± 0.06	1.47 ± 0.10	0.99 ± 0.12	43
3-deaza-PMEA ²⁻	4.60 ± 0.08	3.19 ± 0.06	1.41 ± 0.10	0.93 ± 0.12	43
7-deaza-PMEA ²⁻	3.83 ± 0.08	3.19 ± 0.06	0.64 ± 0.10	0.16 ± 0.12	43

^aThe calculated stability constants are based on the basicity of the phosph(on)ate residues (and their micro-acidity constants where applicable) and the reference-line equations given in Refs. 26 and 36 (see also Fig. 6).

^b*cf.* footnote (a) of Table 1.

^cDefined in analogy to eqn. (3).

^dCalculated with the straight-line equation given in Refs. 26 and 36 and the micro-acidity constant $\text{p}K_{\text{TuMP-H}}^{\text{TuMP}} = 6.24$ (Ref. 35).

TABLE 4—INTRAMOLECULAR EQUILIBRIUM CONSTANTS FOR THE VARIOUS ISOMERIC Cu(PA) COMPLEXES DEFINED IN THE EQUILIBRIUM SCHEMES (10) AND (11), TOGETHER WITH THE PERCENTAGES IN WHICH THE ISOMERS OCCUR. THE VALUES FOR Cu(5'-AMP) ARE GIVEN FOR COMPARISON (FROM REF. 36)

Aqueous solutions; 25°; I = 0.1 M (NaNO₃)^a

Equilibrium scheme (10) involving N7 of the adenine residue :

PA ²⁻	$K_1 = K_{I/tot}$ (Eqn.12a) ^b	$K_{I/O}$ (Eqns. 10,13)	$K_{I/N7}$ (Eqns. 12c,14)	%Cu(PA) _{op} (Eqn.12b)	%Cu(PA) _{cl/O} (Eqns. 4,10)	%Cu(PA) _{cl/N7} (Eqn. 10)
5'-AMP ²⁻	0.86 ± 0.26		0.86 ± 0.26	54 ± 8		46 ± 8
3d-PMEA ²⁻	24.70 ± 5.92	2.02 ± 0.47	22.7 ± 5.9	3.9 ± 0.9	7.9 ± 2.6	88 ± 3

Equilibrium scheme (11) involving N3 of the adenine residue :

PA ²⁻	$K_1 = K_{I/tot}$ (Eqn. 15a) ^b	$K_{I/O}$ (Eqns. 11,13)	$K_{I/O/N3}$ (Eqns.15c,16)	%Cu(PA) _{op} (Eqn. 15b)	%Cu(PA) _{cl/O} (Eqns. 4,11)	%Cu(PA) _{cl/O/N3} (Eqn. 11)
PME ²⁻	2.02 ± 0.47	2.02 ± 0.47		33 ± 5	67 ± 5	
PMEA ²⁻	4.89 ± 0.98	2.02 ± 0.47	1.42 ± 0.74	17 ± 3	34 ± 10	49 ± 10
1d-PMEA ²⁻	28.51 ± 6.80	2.02 ± 0.47	13.1 ± 4.7	3.4 ± 0.8	6.8 ± 2.2	90 ± 2
7d-PMEA ²⁻	3.37 ± 1.01	2.02 ± 0.47	0.67 ± 0.63	23 ± 5	46 ± 15	31 ± 16

^acf.footnote (a) of Table 1. The above results regarding PME²⁻ or PMEA²⁻ and the deaza derivatives of PMEA²⁻ are taken from Refs. 26 and 43, respectively.

^bCalculated with the values listed for log Δ_{Cu/PA} in Table 3.

cises a 'guiding' effect on Cu²⁺ which leads to the preferred broadening of the H2 signal. In agreement with this interpretation is also the bottom part of Fig. 7, where the results for the Cu²⁺/5'-AMP²⁻ system are shown. In accord with the aforementioned macrochelate formation of the phosphate-coordinated Cu²⁺ with N7, the H8 signal is much stronger broadened than the one of H2. Moreover, the relative broadening of the H8 signal of PMEA²⁻ and the H2 signal of 5'-AMP²⁻ is quite alike, indicating that this weak broadening is the result of monodentate Cu²⁺ binding at the N7 and N1 site respectively. To conclude, these line-broadening experiments confirm macrochelate formation for Cu(5'-AMP) and chelate formation for Cu(PMEA) and Cu(1-deaza-PMEA), i.e. in the latter two cases equilibrium scheme (11) is operating.

Quantification of intramolecular equilibria involving three isomers

With the information summarised in the preceding Section we are now in the position to evaluate the quantitative results of Table 3 with regard to the formation degree of the various isomeric complexes occurring in the equilibrium schemes (10) and (11). The mathematical derivation has been described in detail elsewhere^{26,29}.

However, the connection between log Δ_{M/PA} (= log Δ) as defined by equation (5) and the various intramolecular equilibrium constants indicated in the equilibrium scheme (10) is given by equation (12); the corresponding intramolecular equilibrium constants are defined in equations (13) and (14),

$$K_1 = K_{I/tot} = \frac{K_{M(PA)}^M}{K_{M(PA)_{op}}^M} - 1 = 10^{\log \Delta} - 1 \quad (12a)$$

$$= \frac{[M(PA)_{cl/tot}]}{[M(PA)_{op}]}$$

$$= \frac{([M(PA)_{cl/O}] + [M(PA)_{cl/N7}])}{[M(PA)_{op}]} \quad (12b)$$

$$= K_{I/O} + K_{I/N7} \quad (12c)$$

$$K_{I/O} = [M(PA)_{cl/O}]/[M(PA)_{op}] \quad (13)$$

$$K_{I/N7} = [M(PA)_{cl/N7}]/[M(PA)_{op}] \quad (14)$$

Similarly, for the equilibrium scheme (11), equation (15) holds with the additional definition given in equation (16),

$$K_1 = K_{I/tot} = \frac{K_{M(PA)}^M}{K_{M(PA)_{op}}^M} - 1 = 10^{\log \Delta} - 1 \quad (15a)$$

$$= \frac{[M(PA)_{cl/tot}]}{[M(PA)_{op}]}$$

$$= \frac{([M(PA)_{cl/O}] + [M(PA)_{cl/N7}])}{[M(PA)_{op}]} \quad (15b)$$

$$= K_{I/O} + K_{I/O} K_{I/O/N3} = K_{I/O}(1 + K_{I/O/N3}) \quad (15c)$$

$$K_{I/O/N3} = [M(PA)_{cl/O/N3}]/[M(PA)_{cl/O}] \quad (16)$$

It is evident that in case the third isomer involving the adenine residue is not formed, equations (12c) and (15c) reduce to $K_1 = K_{I/tot} = K_{I/O}$; in other words, to the two-isomer problem already defined in equations (7) and (8).

Furthermore, from equations (12) and (15) it is also clear that by using the results obtained for log Δ (= log Δ_{M/PA}) (Table 3), values for $K_{I/tot}$ (= K_1) can be calculated, but that this does not yet allow to solve equations (12c) and (15c) for the individual intramolecular equilibrium constants given there. However, considering that the (phosphonomethoxy)ethyl residue is identical in PME²⁻, in PMEA²⁻ and in its deaza derivatives (Figs. 2 and 4), one may make the justified assumption that the stability of the five-membered chelate (equation 4) in Cu(PME) is the

Fig. 7. Effect of increasing amounts of Cu^{2+} on the ^1H nmr linewidth of H2 and H8 of PME A^{2-} , 1-deaza- PME A^{2-} , and 5'- AMP^{2-} . The ^1H nmr line-broadening experiments were carried out at 25° in D_2O at pD about 8.8 with $[\text{PA}^{2-}] \approx 3.0 \text{ mM}$. For details see Ref. 43.

same as in $\text{Cu}(\text{PME A})$ and the other Cu^{2+} complexes involving the deaza derivatives. Hence, with $K_{\text{I/O}}$ now known, values for $K_{\text{I/N7}}$ and $K_{\text{I/O/N3}}$ may be calculated with equations (12c) and (15c) respectively.

The results of the calculations based on the above reasonings and the given equations as well as on the data of Table 3 are summarised in Table 4. As indicated before, the macrochelate formed by the phosph(on)ate-bound Cu^{2+} with N7 reaches a much larger formation degree for $\text{Cu}(3\text{-deaza-PME A})$ than for $\text{Cu}(5'\text{-AMP})$; this may largely be

due to the higher flexibility of the 'aliphatic' chain in the deaza derivative compared, with the more rigid situation in $5'\text{-AMP}^{2-}$ with its ribose ring. Similarly, the $\text{Cu}(\text{PA})_{\text{cl/O/N3}}$ species is formed, as expected due to the relatively high basicity of N3 in 1-deaza- PME A^{2-} , to a larger percentage with 1-deaza- PME A^{2-} than with PME A^{2-} itself. Further comparisons are possible but the most important conclusion which follows from Table 4 is that all isomers occur in appreciable amounts in equilibrium with each other. For example, for $\text{Cu}(\text{PME A})$ and equilibrium scheme (11) the results show that 17% exist as an isomer with a sole phosphonate coordination, $\text{Cu}(\text{PME A})_{\text{op}}$, 34% form the five-membered chelate involving the ether oxygen, $\text{Cu}(\text{PME A})_{\text{cl/O}}$, and the remaining 49% are due to the isomer containing in addition a $\text{Cu}^{2+}\text{-N3}$ interaction, $\text{Cu}(\text{PME A})_{\text{cl/O/N3}}$.

Mg^{2+} complexes of PME A^{2-} and its deaza derivatives

After studying in detail the coordinating properties of PME A^{2-} and its deaza derivatives with a $3d$ transition metal ion, Cu^{2+} , we considered it as appropriate to extend our studies to one of the alkaline earth ions. We selected Mg^{2+} and determined again by potentiometric pH-titration⁴⁵ the corresponding equilibrium constants. The stability differences between the experimentally measured and the calculated stability constants for the $\text{Mg}(\text{PA})$ complexes according to equation (5) are listed in the second column of Table 5.

TABLE 5—INCREASED COMPLEX STABILITY, $\log \Delta_{\text{Mg/PA}}$ (EQN 5), AND EXTENT OF INTRAMOLECULAR CHELATE FORMATION (EQN 4) IN $\text{Mg}(\text{PA})$ COMPLEXES AS QUANTIFIED BY THE DIMENSIONLESS EQUILIBRIUM CONSTANT K_{I} (EQNS 8, 12a, 13, 15a) AND THE PERCENTAGE OF $\text{Mg}(\text{PA})_{\text{cl/O}}$ FOR AQUEOUS SOLUTIONS AT 25° AND $I = 0.1 \text{ M}$ (NaNO_3)^a

PA^{2-}	$\log \Delta_{\text{Mg/PA}}$	K_{I}^b	% $\text{Mg}(\text{PA})_{\text{cl/O}}^b$
PME A^{2-}	0.22 ± 0.04	0.66 ± 0.16	40 ± 6
PME A^{2-}	0.16 ± 0.06	0.45 ± 0.19	31 ± 9
1-deaza- PME A^{2-}	0.22 ± 0.05	0.66 ± 0.19	40 ± 7
3-deaza- PME A^{2-}	0.14 ± 0.06	0.38 ± 0.18	28 ± 9
7-deaza- PME A^{2-}	0.14 ± 0.06	0.38 ± 0.18	28 ± 9

^acf. footnote (a) of Table 1. The results of rows 1 and 2 are from Ref. 26, and those of rows 3-5 from Ref. 45.

^bcf. footnote (b) of Table 1.

All values listed in Table 5 for $\log \Delta_{\text{Mg/PA}}$ are positive, but also identical within the experimental error limits, including the value for $\text{Mg}(\text{PME})$. This means, the nucleobase moiety has, in agreement with previous observations²⁶, no remarkable effect on the Mg^{2+} -binding properties of the (phosphonomethoxy)ethyl residue, but equilibrium (4) with the formation of the five-membered chelate involving the ether-O is evidently operating, while equilibrium schemes (10) and (11) have no (recognisable) effect. Hence, equation (8) can be applied and the dimensionless equilibrium constant K_{I} quantifying the intramolecular equilibrium (4) can be calculated and this then allows to give also the percentages for $\text{Mg}(\text{PA})_{\text{cl/O}}$;

these values are listed in the final column of Table 5. The formation degree of the closed isomer reaches with approximately 30 to 40% a significant size. It appears safe to conclude that with the other alkaline earth ions also only equilibrium (4) is operating.

Concluding remarks

To the best of my knowledge this is for the first time that with the summarised studies a three-isomer problem has been solved in all its facets, including the binding sites and formation degrees of the various isomeric complexes which occur in solution in equilibrium with each other. By applying various deaza derivatives of PMEAs as well as ^1H nmr line-broadening measurements it was possible to show that N3 of an adenine residue can become an attractive binding site provided the metal ion is brought via a primary coordination into a suitable steric orientation close to the N3 site.

Metal ion binding to N3 of a purine residue has so far only rarely been considered^{46,47}, especially with labile metal ions⁴⁶. It is my belief, however, that N3 may participate in metal ion-binding not only in the complexes of certain nucleotides but also in nucleic acids. For example, in the minor groove of DNA N3 is exposed to the solvent⁴⁸ and therefore, it appears quite likely that metal ions with a reasonable affinity toward N sites may coordinate at this position.

The differences in the metal ion-binding properties between $5'\text{-AMP}^{2-}$ and PMEA^{2-} have been elucidated in the course of this account. Aside from the fact that nucleobase interactions in the metal ion complexes of $5'\text{-AMP}^{2-}$ occur with N7 and in the case of PMEA^{2-} with N3, the main difference is the metal ion interaction with the ether-O in the $-\text{CH}_2\text{-O-CH}_2\text{-PO}_3^{2-}$ residue of PMEA^{2-} which gives rise to the intramolecular equilibrium (4). It needs to be emphasised that exactly this ether-O atom is crucial for the antiviral action of $\text{PMEA}^{15,16}$. Deletion or replacement of this O atom by other atoms or groups leads to a loss or at least to a significant reduction of the biological activity. It is tempting to speculate that these two observations, i.e. the metal ion-binding properties of this ether-O atom and its necessity for the biological activity, are connected with each other.

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